

Design, fabrication and mechanical properties of in situ synthesized titanium matrix composites

Weijie LU*, Xianglong GUO, Di ZHANG, Jining QIN

State Key Laboratory of Metal Matrix Composites, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Dongchuan Road 800#, Shanghai 200240, China (*Corresponding author: luweijie@sjtu.edu.cn)

ABSTRACT: Titanium matrix composites are in situ synthesized by common casting and hot working technology. The combination of reinforcements is optimized, and TiB, TiC and rare earth oxides are chosen to strengthen titanium matrix composites. The orientation relationships between reinforcements and matrix are examined, and the orientation relationships between reinforcements are revealed. Microstructure of titanium matrix composites with different reinforcement volume fractions is studied. Mechanical property tests show titanium matrix composites with reinforcements volume fraction of 2.8% exhibit better high temperature tensile properties, and the strengthening mechanism can be summarized as two reasons: the load bearing effect of TiB short fibers and the dispersion strengthening effect of TiC/La₂O₃ particles.

Key words: TMCs, reinforcements, orientation relationship, mechanical properties

1 Introduction

TMCs offer considerable potential for improvement in various mechanical properties over conventional titanium alloys, especially stiffness, strength and wear resistance [1-3]. Traditionally, titanium matrix composites are processed by powder metallurgy, liquid phase casting and mechanical alloying, however, these methods are to some extent not ideal because of the shortcoming they showed, for example, the interface reaction and high cost. In recent years, in situ technology [4-5] is developed to process TMCs because it overcomes the shortcomings of traditional methods. However, some key problems should be settled to ensure the good performance of the TMCs, for instance, the combination, distribution, orientation, shape and content of the reinforcements should be carefully controlled.

2 Design of titanium matrix composites

TiB, TiC, Nd₂O₃, and Y₂O₃ are selected to be reinforcements for TMCs because they possess several advantages compared with other reinforcements. Firstly, there are no interface reactions between those reinforcements and titanium matrix, secondly, the compatibility between reinforcements and titanium, from the perspectives of thermodynamic, density, coefficient of thermal

expansion, is better than other reinforcements [6-8]. Thermodynamic calculation results of the reactions used to acquire the in situ TMCs are summarized in figure 1. It can be seen that ΔG of every reaction is lower than zero, so the reactions can occur, and TMCs can be acquired.

3 Microstructures analysis

3.1 Phase identification

In the present research, three kinds of TMCs are synthesized and their compositions are shown in table 1. XRD profiles of TMCs are shown in Figure 2. It is obvious that Ti, TiB, TiC, Y₂O₃ and Nd₂O₃ diffraction peaks are observed in the XRD profiles, which indicates that the in situ reactions summarized in Fig.1 take place and result in various reinforcements.

3.2 Microstructure observation

The microstructures of TMCs are shown in Fig.3. According to previous studies [9], the short fibers are TiB and the equiaxed particles are TiC or Y₂O₃ and Nd₂O₃, it can be seen that those reinforcements are distributed uniformly on the matrix.

3.3 Orientation relationships

In order to analyse the orientation relationships

between reinforcements and matrix alloy, HDTEM is used to examine the interface structures.

HDTEM analysis (Fig.4) reveals that the orientation relationships between TiB and Ti matrix are:

$$[001]_{\text{TiB}}//[0001]_{\text{Ti}}; (020)_{\text{TiB}}//(2\bar{1}\bar{1}0)_{\text{Ti}}; (200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}\bar{1}$$

$$00)_{\text{Ti}}; [010]_{\text{TiB}}//[1\bar{1}\bar{2}0]_{\text{Ti}}; (001)_{\text{TiB}}//(0001)_{\text{Ti}};$$

$$(200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}\bar{1}00)_{\text{Ti}}. \text{ The orientation relationships}$$

between Ti and Y_2O_3 are: $[100]_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//[0\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}]_{\text{Ti}}$;

$$(044)_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//(01\bar{1}\bar{2})_{\text{Ti}}; [110]_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//[1\bar{2}\bar{1}\bar{3}]_{\text{Ti}}; (\bar{2}$$

$$23)_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//(01\bar{1}\bar{1})_{\text{Ti}}; [010]_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//[1\bar{1}\bar{2}0]_{\text{Ti}}; (400)_{\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3}//(\bar{1}\bar{1}$$

$00)_{\text{Ti}}$. And the orientation relationships between TiC and TiB are: $[001]_{\text{TiB}}//[001]_{\text{TiC}}; (010)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}10)_{\text{TiC}};$

$$(200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}10)_{\text{TiC}}; [010]_{\text{TiB}}//[110]_{\text{TiC}};$$

$$(001)_{\text{TiB}}//(001)_{\text{TiC}}; (200)_{\text{TiB}}//(\bar{1}10)_{\text{TiC}}$$

HRTEM also reveals that the interface between titanium matrix and reinforcements is clear, and no interface reaction happens, so, the reinforcements and the matrix alloy combine well. The discovery of the orientation relationships between reinforcements and titanium matrix provides evidences for the controlling of the interfaces.

4 Effect of reinforcements on high temperature mechanical properties of in situ synthesized TMCs.

Four types of in situ TMCs (Table.2) with different volume fraction of reinforcements are synthesized by common casting and hot working technology

according to reactions: $5\text{Ti} + \text{B}_4\text{C} = 4\text{TiB} + \text{Ti}$ and

$12\text{Ti} + [\text{O}] + 2\text{LaB}_6 = 12\text{TiB} + \text{La}_2\text{O}_3$. The composition of the matrix alloy is similar to IMI834.

4.1 Microstructure and TiB whiskers aspect ratio distribution

Fig.5(a-e) shows the microscopy of the matrix alloy and TMCs along the forging direction. The short fibers are TiB and the near-equiaxed particles are TiC. The TiB short fibers are observed with a good alignment along the forging direction. Moreover, the size of TiC particles rises as the volume fraction of the reinforcements rises. The TiB fibers also become stubbier along with the rising volume fraction. La_2O_3 can not be observed clearly in the optical microscopy.

4.2 High temperature tensile properties

Fig.6(a) shows the aspect ratio distribution of TiB short fibers. It can be seen that with the increase of reinforcement volume fraction, the average aspect ratio of the TMCs decreases. However, according to equation (1), it can be calculated that at 600°C , 650°C and 700°C , the critical aspect ratios for the TiB fibers are 4.4, 5.6 and 7.0 respectively.

Fig.6(b) shows the high temperature fracture strength of IMI834, Ti1100, TP650 and TMCs with different reinforcements volume fractions. Compared with titanium alloys, the strength of the TMCs is greatly increased. At 600°C , TMC1 with the medium volume fraction of reinforcements show the highest strength. For higher temperatures at 650°C and 700°C , TMC4 with the lowest volume fraction of reinforcements shows the highest strength. The shear lag theory developed by Cox [10] can be used to model the strength of the TMCs. To express the stress distribution, a parameter called critical aspect ratio (AR_c) of the short fiber is introduced:

$$\text{AR}_c = \frac{l_c}{d} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{fb}}}{2\tau_m} \quad (1)$$

l_c is the critical length and d is the diameter of the short fiber, σ_{fb} is the ultimate tensile strength of the short fiber and τ_m is the shear strength of the matrix alloy. For the short fibers with aspect ratio (AR) lower than AR_c , interfacial debonding occurs before fracture of short fibers, which can be called “inefficiently strengthening”. One fiber bears an average load σ_f transferred from the matrix:

$$\sigma_f = \tau_m \text{AR} \quad (2)$$

For the short fibers with AR higher than AR_c , fracture of short fibers occurs before

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_{fb} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_{fb}}{4\tau_m AR}\right) \quad (3)$$

According to formulae (1)–(3), the strength of the composite σ_{cb} can be given as:

$$\sigma_{cb} = \sum_i^{AR_i < AR_c} \nu_i \tau_m AR_i + \sum_j^{AR_j > AR_c} \nu_j \sigma_{fb} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_{fb}}{4\tau_m AR_j}\right) + \quad (4)$$

The AR of TMCs4 distributes in higher region than the other TMCs, so the TiB fibers in TMCs4 can effectively bear the strength because of their higher aspect ratios. This explains why TMCs4 shows higher fracture strength than other TMCs at 650°C and 700°C.

5 Conclusion

- (1) TiB, TiC, La_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 reinforced TMCs are synthesized by in situ technology.
- (2) Orientation relationships between titanium matrix alloy and reinforcements are revealed by HRTEM technology, and the orientation relationships between various reinforcements are also studied.
- (3) Composites with 2.8% volume fraction reinforcements show the best high temperature mechanical properties due to the effectively strengthening of TiB fibers in the high temperature range

Fig. 1 Thermodynamic calculation results of various reactions

Fig.2 XRD diffraction patterns of (1) TMCs1 (2) TMCs2 (3) TMCs3

Fig.3 Micrographs of TMCs with different reinforcements (a) TMCs1 (b)TMCs2 (c) TMCs 3

Fig.4 High resolution TEM of interface between (a)Ti-TiB (b) Ti-TiB (c) Ti- Y_2O_3 (d) TiB-TiC

Fig. 5 Optical microscopy of the matrix alloy and TMCs along the forging direction: (a) TMC1, (b) TMC2, (c) TMC3, (d) TMC4 and (e) matrix alloy.

Fig.6 (a) Aspect ratio distribution of TiB short fibers and (b)high temperature Fracture strength of the specimens

Table.1 Compositions of different kinds of TMCs

Sample No.	TiB / vol.%	TiC / vol.%	Nd ₂ O ₃ / wt.%	Y ₂ O ₃ /wt.%
TMCs1	5	-	3	-
TMCs2	5	-	-	3
TMCs3	5	1.25		3

Table.2 Volume fractions of reinforcements in titanium alloy matrix composites

Sample	Reinforcement (vol%)		
	TiB	TiC	La ₂ O ₃
Matrix alloy	-	-	-
TMC1	3.96	0.42	0.62
TMC2	8.15	1.26	0.59
TMC3	8.29	1.71	-
TMC4	2.25	-	0.75

6 References

[1] Abkowitz S, Abkowitz SM, Fisher H, Schwartz PJ.

CermeTi[®] discontinuously reinforced Ti-matrix composites: manufacturing, properties and applications. JOM, 56 (5), 37-41,2004.

[2] Saito T. The automotive application of discontinuously reinforced TiB-Ti composites. JOM 56 (5):33-36, 2004.

[3] Larsen JM, Russ SM, Jones JW. An evaluation of fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites for advanced high temperature aerospace applications. Metallurgical Materials Transactions A. 26 (12): 3211–23, 1995.

[4] Ranganath S. A review on particulate-reinforced titanium matrix composites. Journal of Materials Science,32 (1): 1-6,1997.

[5] Tjong SC, Mai YW. Processing-structure-property aspects of particulate- and whisker-reinforced titanium matrix composites. Composites Science and Technology, 68 (3-4): 583-601, 2008.

[6] Lu WJ, Zhang D, Zhang XN, Wu RJ. HREM study of TiB/Ti interfaces in a TiB-TiC in situ composite. Scripta Materialia, 44 (7): 1069-1075, 2001.

[7] Konitzer DG, Loretto MH. Microstructural assessment of Ti-6Al-4V-TiC metal matrix composite. Acta Metallurgica, 37 (2):397-406, 1989.

[8] Yang ZF, Lu WJ, Qin JN, Zhang D. Microstructure and tensile properties of in situ synthesized (TiC+TiB+Nd2O3)/Ti-alloy composites at elevated temperature. Materials Science and Engineering A. 425 (1-2): 185-191, 2006.

[9] Z.F. Yang, W.J. Lu, D. Xu, J.N. Qin, D. Zhang, J. Alloys Compd. 419,76–80, 2006.

[10] V. de Castro, T. Leguey, A. Munoz, M.A. Monge, R. Pareja, Mater. Sci.Eng. A, 422 , 189–197,2006.